

Modelling and Development of a Metaheuristic Algorithm for a Hybrid Solar PV/Wind/Fuel-Cell System with Energy Storage for Grid-Connected Distribution: A Case Study of the Maiduguri 132 KV Network

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a rule-based EMS (REMS) optimized by a nature-inspired Particle Swarm Optimization and Greywolf Optimization Algorithm (PSO-GWO) for long-term capacity planning of a grid-independent microgrid in incorporating a wind turbine, a photovoltaic, a battery (BT) bank and a diesel generator (). In which, a rule based algorithm is used to implement an EMS to prioritize the usage of RES and coordinate the power flow of the proposed microgrid components. Subsequently, an attempt is made to explore and confirm the efficiency of the proposed REMS incorporated with PSO-GWO. The ultimate goal of the objective function is to minimize the cost of energy (COE) and the deficiency of power supply probability (DPSP). The performance of the REMS is examined via a long-term simulation study to ascertain the REMS resiliency and to ensure the operating limit of the BT storage is not violated. The result of the PSO-GWO is compared with Greywolf Optimization (GWO), particle swarm optimization (PSO) and a cuckoo search algorithm (CSA). The simulation results indicate that the proposed technique's superiority is confirmed in terms of convergence to the optimal solution. The simulation results confirm that the proposed REMS has contributed to better adoption of a cleaner energy production system, as the scheme significantly reduces fuel consumption, CO₂ emission and COE by 92.4%, 92.3% and 79.8%, respectively as compared to the conventional Dgen. The comparative

evaluation of the algorithms shows that REMS-PSO-GWO yields a better result as it offers the least COE (objective function), at \$0.22326/kW h, as compared to the REMS-GWO at \$0.3656/kWh, REMS-CSA at \$0.3662/kWh and REMS PSO at \$0.3647/kWh, for the desired DPSP of 0%. Finally, sensitivity analysis is performed to highlight the effect of uncertainties on the system inputs that may arise in the future.

Keywords: Hybrid Optimization Algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization, Grey Wolf Optimization Exploration, Exploitation, Renewable Energy Sources, Energy Management Scheme.

INTRODUCTION

Electricity is the key driving force in today's world. It is deeply integrated into every aspect of human life, from daily chores to the global economy. The economic development of a country is strongly associated with its use of electricity. This planet is being harmed both directly and indirectly by the electricity generation process on which we rely so heavily. The energy sectors of nearly all countries are heavily dependent on fossil fuels, posing a significant threat to our environment [1,2]. Electricity production processes play an invaluable part in driving warming by emitting greenhouse gases [3]. A substantial amount of the world's electricity is generated from fossil fuels such as coal, natural gas, and oil. When these fuels are burned to produce electricity, they release carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. The electricity generation sector led to 30 % of the total GHG emissions shown in Fig. 1 among the other sectors that emit major amounts of greenhouse gases [4]. These greenhouse gases hold heat and contribute to the greenhouse effect, leading to global warming and its associated consequences, such as rising temperatures, melting ice caps, and extreme weather events. It is essential to move toward cleaner and more sustainable energy sources to address these issues. Renewable energy, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, presents a viable solution. By adopting these technologies, it is possible to lessen reliance on fossil fuels and lessen the environmental harm that traditional power generation techniques cause [5, 6].

. In this paper, an autonomous hybrid energy system made up of a photovoltaic panel, a wind turbine, a battery, and a fuel-powered generator (diesel generator) is designed, taking into account the meteorological parameters of the region under study to estimate the power output of the wind turbines and photovoltaic panels. An energy management strategy (EMS) is suggested to coordinate the flow of energy between the various energy sources. This study aims to design an optimized autonomous hybrid energy system that meets load demand and ensures reliability, cost-effectiveness, and pollution reduction in a given area. The loss of power supply probability (LPSP) is taken into account to study the reliability of the Microgrid (MG). To tackle the problem of optimal sizing of the proposed Microgrid components, four multiobjective optimization algorithms namely the hybrid Particle Swarm Optimization and Gray wolf Optimization (PSO-GWO) [6] is used. These algorithms are characterized by their simplicity of construction and by the fact that they require fewer control parameters. Our study is based on real solar radiation, wind speed, and temperature data recorded or the remote area of Maiduguri, in the North eastern region of the province of Nigeria.

2. Modeling of grid-independent microgrid test-case system

This section describes the problem by presenting the formation, components, and the power flow of the proposed grid-independent microgrid that is used as the test-case system to confirm the efficacy of the devised optimal capacity planning procedure. It also outlines the microgrid operational scheme that is used in the process of computing for the optimal capacities of the microgrid components. It then presents the projected climatological condition of the case study and power demand data streams, which were used as input data for the analysis. The structure of the proposed grid-independent microgrid is given in Fig.2. It incorporates WT, a BT bank, Dgen, PV modules, a residential load, and converters.

2.1. Mathematical modeling and parameters of the microgrid units.

In this section, the elements of the proposed grid-independent microgrid that are considered in the optimum capacity planning approach are modeled mathematically. The specifications, technical and economic parameters, and product models of components are also presented.

The mathematical modeling of the photovoltaic (PV):

The power output of the solar photovoltaic field is determined by the number of solar panels N_{PV} , the nominal power of each solar panel under standard test conditions (PSTC), solar radiation ($G(t)$), cell temperature ($T_C(t)$), and the various losses caused by the efficiency of the converters, cables, and so on (Losses). Equation (3.1) gives the expression for calculating the power generated by the PV field over time.

$$P_{PV}(t) = N_{PV} \times P_{STC} \times \frac{G(t)}{G_{ref}} \times [1 + \alpha_p \times (T_c(t) - 25)] \times F_{losses} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, α_p is the temperature coefficient and G_{ref} , is the irradiance corresponding to standard measurement conditions (STC), which has a value of 1000 W/m². Equation (2) is used to calculate the temperature T_c of the cells.

$$T_c(t) = T_a(t) + \left(\frac{NOCT - 20}{800}\right) \times G(t) \quad (2)$$

The main constrain in design of the PV array is the area and this constrain area which is available for setting PV array in maximum power and maximum current. With an initial cost and the life time of the project is considered to be equal to the life span of the PV modules the replacement cost of the PV array is negligible.

The mathematical modeling of the wind turbine system:

The wind field’s energy depends not only on the wind velocity at t, but also on the technical characteristics of the wind turbine model used. Equation (3) is employed to calculate the wind field’s output power [9].

$$P_{WT}(v) = N_{WT} \times \begin{cases} 0, v < v_{ci} \\ P_{rated} \times \frac{v - v_{ci}}{v_r - v_{ci}}, v_{ci} \leq v \leq v_r \\ P_{rated}, v_r \leq v \leq v_{co} \\ 0, v > v_{co} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Using Equation (4) [14], the wind speed v at height H can be determined based on the known wind speed v_0 at height H_{10} .

$$v(H) = v_0 \times \left(\frac{H}{H_{10}}\right)^\alpha \quad (4)$$

Here, α represents the Hellmann exponent, which can be calculated with Equation (5).

$$\alpha = \frac{0.37 - 0.088 \cdot \ln v_0}{1 - 0.088 \cdot \ln(H_{10}/10)} \quad (5)$$

The main constraint that has been considered in the design of the wind system is its rotor swept area, this value is constrained by both budget and the available area for the project implementation. Usually, the life time of the wind turbine is shorter than the lifetime to PV array, so it is necessary to purchase new wind turbine to replace the existing ones. The number of times the wind turbines need to be replaced will represents the life of the wind turbine. The salvage value of the wind turbine is assumed to decrease linearly when the turbine operates along its lifetime.

SMES Energy Storage System Modeling:

SMESs can store excess or surplus energy produced by the hybrid system and release it when needed to meet peak load demand, rather than limiting it when load demand is low. This can be done until long-term energy sources are connected to the system during the day. In other words, SMESs can act as loads to store energy while charging and generators to release or transfer energy while discharging. Reactive power can also be delivered or absorbed. The SMES had two modes of operation, as explained below [10].

a. **Charging mode:** When the hybrid system power P_{sys} exceeds the load demand P_L (i.e., $P_L - P_{sys} < 0$), this mode of operation happens.

$$P_{exch}(t) = \max \left\{ -\Delta P(t), \frac{(E_{exch}(t-1) - E_{exch-max}(t))}{\Delta t \times \eta_{ch}}, -P_{exch-rated} \right\} \quad (6)$$

$$E_{exch}(t) = \min \{ (E_{exch}(t-1) - P_{exch-ch}(t) \times \Delta t \times \eta_{ch}), E_{exch-max} \} \quad (7)$$

b. **Discharging mode:** When the load demand P_L is higher than the hybrid system power P_{sys} (i.e., $P_L - P_{sys} > 0$), this mode of operation happens.

$$P_{exch}(t) = \max \left\{ |\Delta P(t)|, \frac{(E_{exch}(t-1) - E_{exch-min}(t)) \times \eta_{dis}}{\Delta t}, P_{exch-rated} \right\} \quad (8)$$

$$E_{exch}(t) = \max \left\{ \left(E_{exch}(t-1) - \frac{P_{exch-dis} \times \Delta t}{\eta_{dis}} \right), E_{exch-min} \right\} \quad (9)$$

State of charge (SOC) represents an index of the energy stored in the SMES, with an initial value ($SOC_{initial}$) to be optimized for each SMES serving different load models [11].

Inverters

The inverters must be able to convert the DC power produced by the photovoltaic array, batteries, and fuel cells into AC power that can be fed into the grid. Additionally, the inverters must be bidirectional so that excess energy from the wind system can be used to charge the batteries and hydrogen tank [8].

$$\begin{cases} P_{invt} \geq P_{PV}(t) + P_{dis}(t) + P_{FC}(t) \\ P_{invt} = k \times \max(P_{PV}(t) + P_{dis}(t) + P_{FC}(t)) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Where, k represents inverter sizing safety factor.

The main constraint which is considered in the design of the storage system is its capacity in Megawatt (MW). The battery life time is expected to be less than the life time of the project. Hence the batteries have to be replaced at a regular interval. The get back value of the batteries is expected to be negligible.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The simulation results obtained based on the methodologies that addressed the research objectives is discussed. The results obtained from the simulations are presented in this section.

Fig.1. Convergence process of the applied algorithms

The ideal convergence characteristic of the applied algorithms over one run 50 iterations is depicted in Fig. 1. The ordinate of the convergence curve represents the COE estimate and offers a platform for the comparison of the applied metaheuristic algorithms, whereas the abscissa represents the iteration count.

At the start of the iteration process, the COE values are \$0.22326, \$0.3951/ kW h, \$0.3958/kW h, and \$0.3857/kW h for REMS-GWO, REMS-CSA, and REMS-PSO, respectively. Afterward, the values decrease for all the applied algorithms during the iteration process. This means that the algorithms minimize the COE by moving towards the promising regions of the search landscape and eventually stop when the maximum iteration is reached. Consequently, a decrease in the objective function is vital because it leads to having extra information about the optimal values of the design variables. A thorough examination of the convergence curve indicates that REMS-PSO-GWO yields a better result as it offers the minimum objective function of \$0.22326/kW h, followed by REMS-CSA with \$0.3662/kWh and REMS-PSO with \$0.3674/kW h. Nevertheless, the REMS-GOA convergence period in the minimum condition is 17 s and better than the REMS-CSA, which is 25s. The REMS-PSO converges to the minimum condition at 7s because PSO is prone to premature convergences [7]. Full details of the results obtained for the considered microgrid in the case of DPSP Desired = 0% are presented in Table 1. The minimum COE, which is regarded as the best choice, is \$0.3656/kW h, as determined by employing the REMS-GOA method. Ranked second is convergence found by REMS-CSA, and Rank third is the one found by REMS-PSO. Thus, it can be concluded that the proposed REMS-GOA offers better performance in all aspects and can successfully be used to find the optimal solution of a complex micro grid design problem compared to its counterparts.

Table1: Optimal results obtained for the grid-independent microgrid for DPSP Desired = 0%.

	REMS- PSO- GWO	REMS- GWO	REMS- CSA	REMS -PSO
DPSP _{Desire}	0	0	0	0
Autonomy days	9	3	3	2
Number of PV panels	45	26	29	30
Number of WT	1	4	6	7
D _{gen} capacity (KW)	5	5	5	5
BSS capacity (KWh)	45.2	45.2	45.2	45.2
COE (\$/KWh)	0.22326	0.3656	0.3662	0.3647
System capital cost (\$)	45,457.2	47,572.	55,346.2	58,937.

Energy Balance Analysis

The amount of energy flow based on running the program simulating the REMS of the microgrid using the optimum capacities of its component obtained by the proposed optimal capacity planning approach is shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 2 (a, b, c and d) illustrate the total and percentage contribution of power produced by the energy sources. Such analysis can be applied to other operational horizons (for example, for the whole project's life span) by simply changing and adapting the input parameters to the model. One other point that should not be ignored is the size of the microgrid element computed using the proposed optimal capacity approach for the same operational project lifespan when performing such an analysis. This mechanism will avert the occurrence of discrepancies between the demand and supply within the microgrid. As demonstrated in Fig. 2, a total of energy generated from difference configuration.

2(a) the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when PSO was used.

Figure 4.2 the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when PSO was used. It was observed from Fig. 2a, that a total of 36% of the energy generated by the microgrid comes from the PV array, and 26% is from the wind, diesel and Battery contributed 11% and 6%, respectively.

2(b) the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when CSA was used.

Fig.2b shows the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when CSA was used. It was also observed from Fig. 2b, that a total of 37% of the energy generated by the microgrid comes from the load, and 27% is from the wind, 9% came from both diesel and Battery while 18% contribution came from PV.

2(c) the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when GWO was used

Similarly, Fig.2c shows the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when GWO was used. It was also seen from the simulation results that, a total of 36% of the energy generated by the microgrid comes from the load, and 38% is from the wind, 11% came from both diesel and load while 4% contribution came from PV.

2(d) the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when PSO-GWO was used.

Fig.2d illustrates the percentage contribution of electricity generation by the system when hybrid PSO-GWO was used. It was noticed from Fig. 2d, that a total of 47% of the energy generated by the microgrid comes from the PV array, and 30% is from the load, diesel and Battery contributed 4% and 18%, respectively.

5. CONCLUSION

This study considered a conceptual grid-independent microgrid to confirm the validity of the proposed EMS and optimal capacity planning method. The microgrid is meant to meet the energy demand of the Maiduguri residential community situated in Borno State, Nigeria. The RE sources in the proposed microgrid can be updated depending on the potential of other regions. Accordingly, the PV and WT were considered as the main energy sources in the microgrid. Furthermore, since the optimal capacity planning problems of micro grids are nonlinear and non-convex combinational optimization problems, to make it amenable to other mathematical optimization methods, the performance of the proposed REM-GOA method is evaluated through a comparative study with REM-PSO-GWO, REM-GWO, REM-PSO and REMS-CSA in terms of optimality of the solution and its convergence when applied to the optimal equipment capacity planning of a conceptualized microgrid for the considered case region. The present study shown has demonstrated that REM-PSO-GWO yields a better result as it offers the minimum objective function of \$0.22326/kWh, compared to REMS-CSA, REMS-GWO and REMS-PSO which yields a COE of \$0.3662/kWh, \$0.3656/kWh and \$0.3674/kWh respectively at DPSP Desired = 0% . The simulation results have also indicated that the proposed can REMS has significantly reduced the CO₂emission, FC, and COE by 92.3%, 92.4%, 79.8% and 78.5% respectively.

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